

QSPR with TAU indices : molar thermochemical properties of diverse functional acyclic compounds

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Molar thermochemical properties (heat of vaporization and boiling point) of diverse functional acyclic compounds have been correlated with TAU indices to unravel the diagnostic feature of the TAU scheme. It was found that, in cases of both the properties, TAU relations could satisfactorily explain the variances of the thermochemical parameters. Moreover, specific contributions of functionality, branching, shape and size factors to the thermochemical properties could be found out from the relations. In general, the properties increase with increase in molecular bulk and functionality, and decrease with increase in branching. Further, boiling point specifically increase with increase in number of hydroxy groups in alcohols and presence of halogen atoms in halocarbons.

Topological descriptors formulated in graph theoretical approaches¹⁻⁵ have been proved to contain structural information to a significant extent^{6,7} and these have been successfully employed to model a variety of physico-chemical properties and biological activities of organic molecules⁸⁻¹⁵. These numerical descriptors of chemical structures have also been used for the classification purpose of organic molecules towards a target property and activity¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Discriminating "drug-like" from "non-drug-like" compounds, which has been an emerging topic in drug research, has also been attempted with various topological descriptors¹⁹ which can efficiently encode chemical information like size, shape, branching, functionality, cyclicity, aromaticity, etc. Recently, Estrada has suggested that 3D structural parameters can also be predicted from 2D (topological) descriptors⁷. The concept of recently developed overall molecular connectivity is a step of unfolding the ideas of molecular connectivity by combining them with those of molecular complexity²⁰. Recent advances in the development of graph theoretical descriptors in physical organic chemistry and pharmaceutical sciences indicate potential of this approach for modeling of physico-chemical and biological data maintaining both statistical and physical meaning⁷.

In late eighties, topochemically arrived unique (TAU) descriptors were introduced²¹⁻²⁴ in valence electron mobile

(VEM) environment and claimed to have significant improvement over molecular connectivity from the view point of diagnostic power for unveiling specific contributions of molecular size, shape, functionality, branching, etc. The uniqueness of the scheme is that different topochemical descriptors are derived by sequentially partitioning the first order composite topochemical index into different parts and thus providing an obvious physical meaning to each of the descriptors. A series of comparative QSPR studies have been reported²⁵⁻²⁸ to model different biological and physico-chemical properties to show superiority of the scheme over other well-accepted ones. Recently, we have reported QSPR of water solubility of diverse functional compounds using TAU parameters²⁹.

The first order composite topochemical index (T) is defined as

$$T = \sum_{i < j} E_{ij} = \sum_{i < j} (V_i V_j)^{0.5} \quad (1)$$

where E_{ij} represents VEM edge weight of the edge between i -th and j -th vertices and V_i is VEM vertex weight of the i -th vertex. V_i is defined as :

$$V_i = \lambda_i / \theta_i \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_i = \text{Core count of the } i\text{-th vertex} = (Z - Z') / Z^v \quad (3)$$

$$\theta_i = \text{VEM count of the } i\text{-th vertex}$$

$$= 8 - (2h + 1.5v + n), \text{ when unsaturation is not present} \quad (4)$$

$$= 0.5v + 2\pi, \text{ when unsaturation is present} \quad (5)$$

h = number of hydrogen atom(s) bonded, v = number of sigma bonds (other than hydrogen), n = number of nonbonded electrons attached to the atom, π = number of pi-bonds associated with the atom.

In case of a heteroatom, VEM edge weight of an edge incident upon the heteroatom is given a negative value (i.e., multiplied by -1). The composite index T can further be divided into two components: skeletal index T_R and functionality F . The skeletal index T_R is the topochemical index of the reference alkane that may be obtained by replacing heteroatom with carbon and removing the multiple bonds that may be present. Again, functionality F is defined as:

$$F = T_R - T \quad (6)$$

The skeletal index T_R is further partitioned to derive branching index B .

$$B = T_N - T_R \quad (7)$$

T_N is topochemical index of the corresponding normal alkane.

N_V of the reference alkane may further be partitioned into N_P (number of methyl carbons), N_I (number of methylene carbons), and N_B (number of branched carbons). N_B is composed of N_Y (number of tertiary carbons) and N_X (num-

ber of quaternary carbons). Thus, obviously,

$$N_V = N_P + N_I + N_X + N_Y \quad (8)$$

Vertex count (N_V) of the hydrogen-suppressed molecular formula is purely a constitutional parameter because it may be obtained directly from the molecular formula. Even structural formula is not needed for obtaining the value of N_V . Obviously, any index showing better correlation with physico-chemical or biological activity than that shown by N_V will have significance in the context of QSPR/QSAR studies. N_V may be considered as the molecular bulk parameter whereas N_B , N_P , N_X and N_Y represent shape parameters. The functionality contribution and branching parameter are represented by F and B respectively²¹⁻²⁴. The first order VEM skeletal index T_R is considered as the index for intrinsic lipophilicity. All TAU indices are basically derived by sequentially partitioning the first order composite index T into different factors. During development of QSAR equations with TAU parameters, above mentioned hierarchical relations are followed. For obvious reasons, B and N_B , or N_P and N_B , or N_V and N_I are not used in the same equation²⁴.

In the present paper, we have modeled molar thermochemical properties [heat of vaporization ($n = 67$) and boiling point ($n = 136$)] of diverse functional acyclic compounds, encompassing alcohols, alkanes, amines, ethers and halocarbons, with different TAU parameters through multivariate relations. The observed values of the physico-chemical parameters (Table 1) were taken from Ref. 3.

Table 1. Topochemical indices, observed and calculated heat of vaporization (H_V) and boiling point of diverse functional aliphatic compounds

Sl. no.	Compd.	Descriptors			H_V			B_p		
		T	T_R	T_N	Obs. ^a	Calcd.	Calcd. ^d	Obs. ^a	Calcd.	Calcd. ^k
1	Methanol	-0.817	1.000	1.000	8.940	9.031 ^b	11.314	-	-	-
2	Ethanol	0.130	1.414	1.414	10.180	10.204 ^b	9.972	-	-	-
3	<i>n</i> -Propanol	0.630	1.914	1.914	11.340	11.377 ^b	11.176	97.1	99.26 ^e	96.00
4	2-Propanol	0.683	1.731	1.914	10.900	10.598 ^b	9.767	82.4	81.76 ^e	85.24
5	<i>n</i> -Butanol	1.130	2.414	2.414	12.500	12.549 ^b	12.379	117.6	118.46 ^e	117.95
6	2-Methylpropanol	0.985	2.270	2.414	12.150	11.771 ^b	12.103	108.1	110.21 ^e	110.56
7	2-Butanol	1.221	2.269	2.414	11.890	11.771 ^b	10.971	-	-	-
8	2-Methyl-2-propanol	1.092	2.000	2.414	11.140	11.140 ^b	9.870	-	-	-
9	<i>n</i> -Pentanol	1.630	2.914	2.914	13.610	13.722 ^b	13.583	138.0	137.57 ^e	139.89
10	2-Pentanol	1.721	2.769	2.914	12.560	12.944 ^b	12.175	118.9	120.08 ^e	131.07
11	3-Pentanol	1.759	2.807	2.914	12.360	12.944 ^b	12.175	-	-	-
12	2-Methyl-1-butanol	1.523	2.807	2.914	13.040	12.944 ^b	13.302	128.9	129.37 ^e	134.44
13	3-Methyl-1-butanol	1.485	2.769	2.914	13.150	12.944 ^b	13.302	132.0	129.37 ^e	132.50
14	2-Methyl-2-butanol	1.652	2.561	2.914	-	-	-	102.3	104.94 ^e	119.62
15	3-Methyl-2-butanol	1.593	2.641	2.914	12.270	12.166 ^b	11.894	-	-	-
16	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	2.130	3.414	3.414	15.000	14.895 ^b	14.786	157.5	156.73 ^e	161.83

Table-1 (contd.)

17	2,2-Dimethyl-1-butanol	1.837	3.121	3.914	-	-	-	136.7	138.87 ^e	146.90
18	2,3-Dimethyl-1-butanol	1.895	3.179	3.914	-	-	-	145.0	140.33 ^e	149.86
19	3,3-Dimethyl-2-butanol	1.895	2.943	3.914	-	-	-	120.4	121.41 ^e	136.41
20	2-Methyl-1-pentanol	2.023	3.307	3.914	-	-	-	148.0	148.53 ^e	156.38
21	2-Methyl-2-pentanol	2.152	3.061	3.914	-	-	-	123.0	124.09 ^e	141.57
22	4-Methyl-2-pentanol	2.076	3.124	3.914	-	-	-	133.0	131.03 ^e	145.62
23	2-Methyl-3-pentanol	2.131	3.179	3.914	-	-	-	127.5	131.03 ^e	148.43
24	3-Methyl-3-pentanol	2.213	3.121	3.914	-	-	-	136.0	124.05 ^e	144.62
25	<i>n</i> -Heptanol	2.630	3.914	3.914	16.200	16.068 ^b	15.990	176.8	175.89 ^e	183.78
26	2,4-Dimethyl-1-pentanol	2.378	3.662	4.414	-	-	-	159.8	159.49 ^e	170.94
27	2,4-Dimethyl-3-pentanol	2.503	3.551	4.414	-	-	-	140.0	141.99 ^e	163.85
28	3-Ethyl-3-pentanol	2.774	3.682	4.414	-	-	-	142.0	143.21 ^e	169.67
29	<i>n</i> -Octanol	3.130	4.414	4.414	17.000	17.240 ^b	17.194	194.4	195.05 ^e	205.72
30	2-Ethyl-1-hexanol	3.061	4.345	4.414	16.120	16.462 ^b	16.913	-	-	-
31	6-Methyl-1-heptanol	2.985	4.269	4.914	-	-	-	188.0	186.85 ^e	198.33
32	3-Methyl-3-heptanol	3.213	4.121	4.914	-	-	-	163.0	162.37 ^e	188.51
33	4-Methyl-4-heptanol	3.213	4.121	4.914	-	-	-	161.0	162.37 ^e	188.51
34	<i>n</i> -Nonanol	3.630	4.914	4.914	18.600	18.413 ^b	18.397	-	-	-
35	4-Ethyl-4-heptanol	3.567	4.475	5.414	-	-	-	182.0	181.53 ^e	203.01
36	2-Methyl-2-octanol	3.652	4.561	5.414	-	-	-	178.0	181.57 ^e	207.40
37	<i>n</i> -Decanol	4.130	5.414	5.414	19.820	19.586 ^b	19.601	-	-	-
38	Ethanediol	-0.366	1.731	1.914	-	-	-	197.8	176.02 ^f	147.13
39	1,2-Propanediol	-0.064	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	187.4	199.96 ^f	172.45
40	1,3-Propanediol	-0.155	2.414	2.414	-	-	-	214.7	216.39 ^f	181.27
41	1,3-Butanediol	0.436	2.769	2.914	-	-	-	207.5	207.46 ^f	194.39
42	1,4-Butanediol	0.345	2.914	2.914	-	-	-	230.0	223.89 ^f	203.21
43	2,3-Butanediol	0.545	2.641	2.914	-	-	-	181.7	190.96 ^f	186.43
44	Glycerol	-0.810	2.807	2.914	-	-	-	290.0	296.86 ^f	259.64
45	1,5-Pentanediol	0.845	3.414	3.414	-	-	-	238.0	231.39 ^f	225.15
46	2-Methyl-2,4-pentanediol	1.459	3.416	3.914	-	-	-	196.0	196.28 ^f	218.01
47	Ethane	1.000	1.000	1.000	2.264	2.643 ^c	2.636	-	-	-
48	Propane	1.414	1.414	1.414	3.965	3.845 ^c	3.839	-	-	-
49	<i>n</i> -Butane	1.914	1.914	1.914	5.191	5.047 ^c	5.043	-	-	-
50	Isobutane	1.731	1.731	1.914	4.799	4.738 ^c	4.762	-	-	-
51	<i>n</i> -Pentane	2.414	2.414	2.414	6.395	6.249 ^c	6.247	36.1	37.34 ^g	54.53
52	2-Methylbutane	2.269	2.269	2.414	6.030	5.940 ^c	5.966	27.9	31.72 ^g	47.24
53	2,2-Dimethylpropane	2.000	2.000	2.414	5.345	5.496 ^c	5.533	9.5	21.28 ^g	33.53
54	<i>n</i> -Hexane	2.914	2.914	2.914	7.555	7.451 ^c	7.450	68.7	65.94 ^g	76.57
55	2-Methylpentane	2.769	2.769	2.914	7.160	7.142 ^c	7.169	60.2	60.32 ^g	69.18
56	3-Methylpentane	2.807	2.807	2.914	7.255	7.142 ^c	7.169	63.5	61.79 ^g	71.12
57	2,2-Dimethylbutane	2.561	2.561	2.914	6.651	6.698 ^c	6.737	49.7	52.24 ^g	58.58
58	2,3-Dimethylbutane	2.641	2.641	2.914	6.985	6.832 ^c	6.888	57.9	55.35 ^g	62.66
59	<i>n</i> -Heptane	3.414	3.414	3.414	8.739	8.654 ^c	8.654	99.3	94.54 ^g	98.52
60	2-Methylhexane	3.269	3.269	3.414	8.325	8.344 ^c	8.373	90.0	88.91 ^g	91.13
61	3-Methylhexane	3.307	3.307	3.414	8.391	8.344 ^c	8.373	93.4	90.39 ^g	93.06
62	3-Ethylpentane	3.345	3.345	3.414	8.425	8.344 ^c	8.373	93.4	91.86 ^g	95.00

Table-1 (contd.)

63	2,2-Dimethylpentane	3.061	3.061	3.414	7.764	7.900 ^c	7.941	79.2	80.84 ^g	80.53
64	2,3-Dimethylpentane	3.179	3.179	3.414	8.191	8.034 ^c	8.092	89.7	85.42 ^g	86.54
65	2,4-Dimethylpentane	3.124	3.124	3.414	7.872	8.034 ^c	8.092	80.5	83.29 ^g	83.74
66	3,3-Dimethylpentane	3.121	3.121	3.414	7.901	7.900 ^c	7.941	86.0	83.17 ^g	83.59
67	2,2,3-Trimethylbutane	2.943	2.943	3.414	7.669	7.590 ^c	7.660	80.9	76.26 ^g	74.52
68	<i>n</i> -Octane	3.914	3.914	3.914	9.915	9.856 ^c	9.857	125.7	123.14 ^g	120.46
69	2-Methylheptane	3.769	3.769	3.914	9.484	9.546 ^c	9.576	117.7	117.51 ^g	113.07
70	3-Methylheptane	3.807	3.807	3.914	9.521	9.546 ^c	9.576	119.0	118.99 ^g	115.01
71	4-Methylheptane	3.807	3.807	3.914	9.483	9.546 ^c	9.576	117.7	118.99 ^g	115.01
72	3-Ethylhexane	3.845	3.845	3.914	9.476	9.546 ^c	9.576	118.6	120.46 ^g	116.94
73	2,2-Dimethylhexane	3.561	3.561	3.914	8.915	9.102 ^c	9.144	106.9	109.44 ^g	102.47
74	2,3-Dimethylhexane	3.679	3.679	3.914	9.272	9.236 ^c	9.296	115.6	114.02 ^g	108.49
75	2,4-Dimethylhexane	3.662	3.662	3.914	9.029	9.236 ^c	9.296	109.5	113.36 ^g	107.62
76	2,5-Dimethylhexane	3.624	3.624	3.914	9.051	9.236 ^c	9.296	109.1	111.88 ^g	105.68
77	3,3-Dimethylhexane	3.621	3.621	3.914	8.973	9.102 ^c	9.144	112.0	111.77 ^g	105.53
78	3,4-Dimethylhexane	3.717	3.717	3.914	9.316	9.236 ^c	9.296	117.7	115.49 ^g	110.42
79	2-Methyl-3-ethylpentane	3.717	3.717	3.914	9.209	9.236 ^c	9.296	115.7	115.49 ^g	110.42
80	3-Methyl-3-ethylpentane	3.682	3.682	3.914	9.081	9.102 ^c	9.144	118.3	114.13 ^g	108.64
81	2,2,3-Trimethylpentane	3.481	3.481	3.914	8.826	8.792 ^c	8.863	109.9	106.34 ^g	98.40
82	2,2,4-Trimethylpentane	3.416	3.416	3.914	8.402	8.792 ^c	8.863	99.3	103.81 ^g	95.08
83	2,3,3-Trimethylpentane	3.503	3.503	3.914	8.897	8.792 ^c	8.863	114.8	107.19 ^g	99.52
84	2,3,4-Trimethylpentane	3.551	3.551	3.914	9.014	8.926 ^c	9.015	113.5	109.05 ^g	101.96
85	2,2,3,3-Tetramethylbutane	3.250	3.250	3.914	8.410	8.349 ^c	8.431	106.3	97.37 ^g	86.63
86	<i>n</i> -Nonane	4.414	4.414	4.414	11.100	11.058 ^c	11.061	150.8	151.73 ^g	142.40
87	4-Methyloctane	4.307	4.307	4.414	–	–	–	142.5	147.58 ^g	136.95
88	3,3-Diethylpentane	4.243	4.243	4.414	–	–	–	146.2	145.10 ^g	133.69
89	2,2-Dimethylheptane	4.061	4.061	4.414	–	–	–	132.7	138.04 ^g	124.42
90	2,4,4-Trimethylhexane	3.976	3.976	4.414	–	–	–	130.4	134.74 ^g	120.09
91	2,2,5-Trimethylhexane	3.916	3.916	4.414	–	–	–	124.1	132.41 ^g	117.03
92	2,2,4-Trimethylhexane	3.954	3.954	4.414	–	–	–	126.5	133.89 ^g	118.96
93	2,2,3-Trimethylhexane	3.981	3.981	4.414	–	–	–	133.6	134.93 ^g	120.34
94	2,3,3-Trimethylhexane	4.003	4.003	4.414	–	–	–	137.7	135.79 ^g	121.46
95	2,3,5-Trimethylhexane	4.034	4.034	4.414	–	–	–	131.3	136.99 ^g	123.04
96	3,3,4-Trimethylhexane	4.041	4.041	4.414	–	–	–	140.5	137.26 ^g	123.40
97	2,2-Dimethyl-3-ethylpentane	4.019	4.019	4.414	–	–	–	133.8	136.41 ^g	122.28
98	2,4-Dimethyl-3-ethylpentane	4.089	4.089	4.414	–	–	–	136.7	139.12 ^g	125.84
99	2,2,3,3-Tetramethylpentane	3.811	3.811	4.414	9.871	9.551 ^c	9.634	140.3	128.34 ^g	111.68
100	2,2,3,4-Tetramethylpentane	3.853	3.853	4.414	9.478	9.684 ^c	9.786	133.1	129.97 ^g	113.82
101	2,2,4,4-Tetramethylpentane	3.707	3.707	4.414	9.580	9.551 ^c	9.634	122.3	124.30 ^g	106.38
102	2,3,3,4-Tetramethylpentane	3.885	3.885	4.414	9.910	9.684 ^c	9.786	–	–	–
103	<i>n</i> -Decane	4.914	4.914	4.914	12.276	12.260 ^c	12.265	–	–	–
104	<i>n</i> -Dodecane	5.914	5.914	5.914	14.650	14.664 ^c	14.672	–	–	–
105	<i>n</i> -Hexadecane	7.914	7.914	7.914	19.450	19.472 ^c	19.486	–	–	–
106	Propylamine	0.575	1.914	1.914	–	–	–	49.0	51.54 ^h	40.81
107	2-Amino-2-methylpropane	1.053	2.000	2.414	–	–	–	44.4	55.36 ^h	39.28
108	Isopropylmethylamine	0.157	2.269	2.414	–	–	–	50.0	51.24 ^h	60.06

Table-1 (contd.)

109	Diethylamine	0.520	2.414	2.414	-	-	-	56.0	67.19 ^h	66.13
110	<i>n</i> -Butylamine	1.075	2.414	2.414	-	-	-	77.8	75.93 ^h	62.76
111	2-Amino-2-methylbutane	1.613	2.561	2.914	-	-	-	78.0	79.73 ^h	64.34
112	1-Amino-3-methylbutane	1.430	2.769	2.914	-	-	-	95.0	87.81 ^h	77.31
113	Isopentylamine	1.430	2.769	2.914	-	-	-	96.0	87.81 ^h	77.31
114	1-Aminopentane	1.575	2.914	2.914	-	-	-	104.4	100.32 ^h	84.70
115	3-Aminopentane	1.714	2.807	2.914	-	-	-	91.0	91.68 ^h	77.76
116	3-Amino-2,2-dimethylbutane	1.849	2.943	3.414	-	-	-	102.0	89.31 ^h	81.16
117	Diisopropylamine	1.578	3.124	3.414	-	-	-	84.0	96.42 ^h	93.13
118	Butyldimethylamine	0.308	3.269	3.414	-	-	-	95.0	86.65 ^h	109.10
119	Triethylamine	1.025	3.345	3.414	-	-	-	89.0	96.75 ^h	109.09
120	Hexylamine	2.075	3.414	3.414	-	-	-	130.0	124.72 ^h	106.65
121	Dimethylpentylamine	0.808	3.769	3.914	-	-	-	123.0	111.04 ^h	131.05
122	1-Aminoheptane	2.575	3.914	3.914	-	-	-	156.9	149.11 ^h	128.59
123	2-Aminoheptane	2.676	3.769	3.914	-	-	-	142.0	140.47 ^h	119.71
124	Diisobutylamine	2.230	4.124	4.414	-	-	-	139.0	139.73 ^h	139.13
125	Dibutylamine	2.520	4.414	4.414	-	-	-	159.0	164.76 ^h	153.90
126	Tripropylamine	2.525	4.845	4.914	-	-	-	156.0	169.96 ^h	174.91
127	Methylpropylether	0.222	2.414	2.414	-	-	-	38.9	42.59 ⁱ	67.94
128	Methyl <i>t</i> -butylether	0.634	2.561	2.914	-	-	-	55.2	49.68 ⁱ	70.28
129	Ethyl <i>t</i> -butylether	1.511	3.061	3.414	-	-	-	73.1	74.67 ⁱ	89.94
130	<i>sec</i> -Butylethylether	1.658	3.307	3.414	-	-	-	81.0	83.62 ⁱ	103.08
131	Ethyl <i>t</i> -pentylether	2.071	3.621	3.914	-	-	-	101.0	99.67 ⁱ	114.94
132	Butyl isopropylether	2.120	3.769	3.914	-	-	-	108.0	108.62 ⁱ	123.08
133	Hexylmethylether	1.722	3.914	3.914	-	-	-	118.0	117.57 ⁱ	133.77
134	Ethyl pentylether	2.098	3.914	3.914	-	-	-	123.0	117.57 ⁱ	131.49
135	Di- <i>sec</i> -butylether	2.718	4.201	4.414	-	-	-	121.0	124.66 ⁱ	140.55
136	Dibutylether	2.598	4.414	4.414	-	-	-	142.0	142.56 ⁱ	153.43
137	2-Chloropropane	0.179	1.731	1.914	-	-	-	36.5	38.33 ⁱ	64.95
138	<i>tert</i> -Butylchloride	0.655	2.000	2.414	-	-	-	51.0	59.02 ^j	73.87
139	2-Chlorobutane	0.717	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	68.0	66.44 ^j	88.84
140	1-Chloro-2-methylpropane	0.367	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	69.0	78.89 ^j	90.96
141	2-Chlorobutane	0.717	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	78.0	66.44 ^j	88.84
142	3-Chloropentane	1.255	2.807	2.914	-	-	-	97.0	94.47 ^j	112.71
143	2-Bromopropane	-0.478	1.731	1.914	-	-	-	60.0	61.77 ^j	68.94
144	1-Bromopropane	-0.793	1.914	1.914	-	-	-	71.0	79.53 ^j	81.29
145	1-Bromo-2-methylpropane	-0.438	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	91.0	107.60 ^j	95.84
146	2-Bromobutane	0.060	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	91.0	89.83 ^j	92.82
147	3-Bromopentane	0.598	2.807	2.914	-	-	-	118.0	117.91 ^j	116.70
148	2-Iodopropane	-0.939	1.731	1.914	-	-	-	90.0	78.21 ^j	71.74
149	2-Iodobutane	-0.401	2.269	2.414	-	-	-	120.0	106.28 ^j	95.62
150	1-Iodobutane	-0.858	2.414	2.414	-	-	-	130.0	127.75 ^j	106.66
151	2-Iodopentane	0.099	2.769	2.914	-	-	-	142.0	134.35 ^j	117.56
152	1-Iodopentane	-0.358	2.914	2.914	-	-	-	155.0	155.82 ^j	128.61
153	1-Iodoheptane	0.142	3.414	3.414	-	-	-	179.0	183.89 ^j	150.55

Obs : Observed; Calcd. : Calculated.

^aRef. 3; ^bfrom eq. 15; ^cfrom eq. 20; ^dfrom eq. 27; ^efrom eq. 33; ^ffrom eq. 35; ^gfrom eq. 42; ^hfrom eq. 51; ⁱfrom eq. 56; ^jfrom eq. 59; ^kfrom eq. 64.

Multiple linear regression analyses were done using a software program RRR98 developed by one of the authors³⁰. Statistical quality of the equations³¹ was judged by examining the parameters like Q^2 (crossvalidation R^2 or predicted variance), R_a^2 (adjusted R^2 , i.e., explained variance), r or R (correlation coefficient), F (variance ratio) with df (degree of freedom), s (standard error of estimate), $AVRES$ (average of absolute values of residuals) and $SDEP$ (standard error of predictions). Significance of the regression coefficients was judged from standard error of the coefficients. A compound was considered as an outlier for a particular equation when the residual exceeded twice the standard error of estimate of the equation. In case that intercept of an equation was statistically insignificant and omission of the same did not affect the quality of the equation, exclusion of the intercept gave statistically more acceptable equation. PRESS statistics were calculated by "leave-one-out" (LOO) technique³² using programs KRPRES1 and KRPRES2³⁰.

Results and discussion

The relations of heat of vaporization with topochemical indices are shown in Table 2 while those of boiling point are given in Table 3. Regression coefficients of all the equations displayed in Tables 2 and 3 are significant at 95% level and variance ratios are significant at 99% level.

Table 2 shows that first order composite topochemical index can explain 94.0% and predict 92.4% of the variance of heat of vaporization of alcohols. Again, when first order skeletal index is used, the resultant relation shows 98.0% explained variance and 97.7% predicted variance. When the composite index is partitioned into different terms, the resultant relations can explain up to 99.1% of the variance (eqs. 14 and 15). Positive coefficient of vertex count (N_V) in equations 11 to 14 suggests that heat of vaporization of alcohols increases with increase in molecular bulk. Negative coefficients of B , N_P and N_B denote that the property

Table 2. Relations of heat of vaporization (H_v) of alcohols and alkanes with topochemical indices

Eq. no.	Compd.	Regression coefficient(s) and constant*					Statistics			
		β_1 s.e.	β_2 s.e.	β_3 s.e.	β_4 s.e.	α s.e.	Q^2 ($SDEP$)	R_a^2 (r or R)	s ($F(df)$)	$AVRES$ (n)
9	Alcohol	2.307 T 0.133				9.576 0.271	0.924 (0.761)	0.940 (0.971)	0.693 (3.00×10^2 (1, 18))	0.553 (20)
10	"	2.394 T_R 0.077				6.479 0.242	0.977 (0.418)	0.980 (0.991)	0.396 (9.56×10^2 (1, 18))	0.304 (20)
11	"	-4.081 B 0.756	1.163 N_V 0.037			6.642 0.263	0.979 (0.402)	0.984 (0.993)	0.361 (5.77×10^2 (2, 17))	0.250 (20)
12	"	1.179 N_V 0.030	-0.816 N_B 0.113			6.639 0.212	0.987 (0.310)	0.989 (0.995)	0.295 (8.68×10^2 (2, 17))	0.220 (20)
13	"	1.172 N_V 0.026	-0.755 N_P 0.088			8.193 0.306	0.990 (0.270)	0.992 (0.996)	0.258 (1.14×10^3 (2, 17))	0.188 (20)
14	"	1.173 N_V 0.027	-1.409 N_X 0.279	-0.778 N_Y 0.103		6.686 0.183	** (0.996)	0.991 (0.996)	0.264 (7.24×10^2 (3, 16))	0.186 (20)
15	"	4.516 N_P 0.072	1.173 N_I 0.027	-6.923 N_X 0.391	-2.948 N_Y 0.182		** (0.996)	0.991 (0.996)	0.264 (1.35×10^4 (4, 16))	0.186 (20)
16	Alkane	2.395 T 0.021				0.471 0.075	0.996 (0.163)	0.996 (0.998)	0.156 (1.27×10^4 (1, 45))	0.114 (47)
17	"	1.170 N_V 0.026	-0.402 N_P 0.046			1.422 0.235	0.974 (0.415)	0.978 (0.989)	0.388 (1.01×10^3 (2, 44))	0.180 (47)
18	"	1.159 N_V 0.031	-0.496 N_B 0.078			0.653 0.241	0.964 (0.491)	0.968 (0.985)	0.463 (7.04×10^2 (2, 44))	0.276 (47)
19	"	1.171 N_V 0.026	-0.820 N_X 0.101	-0.378 N_Y 0.072		0.604 0.218	0.974 (0.418)	0.977 (0.989)	0.392 (6.60×10^2 (3, 43))	0.176 (47)
20	"	1.322 N_P 0.030	1.202 N_I 0.010	0.209 N_X 0.097	0.772 N_Y 0.059		0.996 (0.155)	0.997 (0.999)	0.145 (4.48×10^4 (4, 43))	0.106 (47)

Table-2 (contd.)

21	Mixed	1.909 T_R 0.301				3.842	0.341	0.373	2.746	2.432
						1.032	(2.794)	(0.619)	(40.274 (1, 65))	(67)
22	"	2.390 T_R 0.053	4.747 F 0.103			0.535	0.978	0.981	0.474	0.231
						0.192	(0.515)	(0.991)	(1.73 × 10 ³ (2, 64))	(67)
23	"	4.709 F 0.129	-2.259 B 0.388	1.170 N_V 0.030		0.530	0.971	0.975	0.546	0.268
						0.233	(0.589)	(0.988)	(8.67 × 10 ² (3, 63))	(67)
24	"	4.672 F 0.126	1.180 N_V 0.029	-0.378 N_P 0.060		1.306	0.973	0.977	0.529	0.266
						0.279	(0.570)	(0.989)	(9.26 × 10 ² (3, 63))	(67)
25	"	4.735 F 0.135	1.172 N_V 0.032	-0.448 N_B 0.089		0.538	0.968	0.973	0.571	0.320
						0.247	(0.613)	(0.987)	(7.89 × 10 ² (3, 63))	(67)
26	"	4.674 F 0.127	1.181 N_V 0.029	-0.785 N_X 0.132	-0.344 N_Y 0.089	0.530	0.972	0.976	0.532	0.261
						0.237	(0.573)	(0.989)	(6.86 × 10 ² (4, 62))	(67)
27	"	4.776 F 0.104	1.204 N_I 0.024	2.897 N_X 0.124	2.126 N_Y 0.086	2.636	0.981	0.984	0.435	0.217
						0.127	(0.472)	(0.993)	(1.03 × 10 ³ (4, 62))	(67)

s.e. = standard error; F values are significant at 99% level [$df = np, n - np - i$. np = no. of predictor variables; $i = 1$ if intercept is present; $i = 0$, otherwise].

* t values of the regression coefficients and constants are significant at 95% level [$df = n - np - i$].

**Leave-one-out could not be applied due to insufficient occurrence of N_X type vertex.

decreases with increase in branching. Again, the impact of quaternary type vertex (N_X) is more than that of tertiary type vertex (N_Y). Because of insufficient occurrence of quaternary type vertex, leave-one-out cross-validation could not be applied for equations 14 and 15. The calculated values of heat of vaporization according to eq. 15 are given in Table 1. 3-Pentanol (**11**) acts as an outlier for eq. 15.

Table 2 shows that the composite index itself can explain and predict 99.6% of the variance of heat of vaporization of alkanes. When the composite index is split into different parameters, impact of different structural aspects (bulk, branching and shape) is obtained. The relations suggest that heat of vaporization of alkanes increases with bulk and decreases with branching. However, in eq. 20, positive coefficients of N_X and N_Y are due to their contribution to N_V , which has positive impact. Effect of branching will be detectable from equations containing N_V term. The calculated values of heat of vaporization according to eq. 20 are given in Table 1. Ethane (**47**), 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (**82**) and 2,2,4,4-tetramethylpentane (**99**) act as outliers for eq. 20.

Table 2 shows that the skeletal index (explained variance 37.3%, predicted variance 34.1%) cannot satisfactorily describe the change of heat of formation of the composite set of compounds (alcohols and alkanes). The relation involving the composite index is further inferior. However, when the composite index is suitably split into different terms, statistically acceptable relations are generated and effects of different structural aspects on heat of vaporiza-

tion become evident. In general, the property increases with increase in bulk and functionality, and decreases with increase in branching. Further, the effect of quaternary type vertex is more than that of tertiary type vertex. The calculated values of the property according to eq. 27 are given in Table 1. Methanol (**1**), 2-propanol (**4**), 2-butanol (**7**) and 2-methyl-2-propanol (**3**) act as outlier for eq. 27.

Table 3 shows that the composite index can explain 75.7% of the variance of boiling point of monohydric alkanols (73.2% cross-validated R^2) while the skeletal index in association with functionality can explain 97.8% of the variance (97.5% cross-validated R^2). Quality of the equations increases further on splitting of T_R . The relations suggest positive contributions of functionality and bulk and negative contributions of branching. The effect of quaternary type vertex is more than that of tertiary type vertex. The calculated values of boiling point according to eq. 33 are shown in Table 1. 3-Methyl-3-pentanol (**24**) acts as an outlier for eq. 33.

Table 3 shows the relations of boiling point of polyols with topochemical indices and these show positive contributions of bulk and functionality as evidenced from the value of regression coefficients. The calculated values of the property according to eq. 35 are shown in Table 1. All compounds fitted well in eq. 35.

Table 3 lists the relations of boiling point of mixed alcohols (monohydric alkanols and polyols). The listed equations show explained variance and predicted variance of

Table 3. Relations of boiling point (B_p) of acyclic compounds with topochemical indices

Eq. no.	Compd.	Regression coefficient(s) and constant*					Statistics					
		β_1 s.e.	β_2 s.e.	β_3 s.e.	β_4 s.e.	β_5 s.e.	β_6 s.e.	α s.e.	Q^2 (SDEP)	R_a^2 (r or R)	s (F(df))	AVRES (n)
28	Monools	30.360 T 3.293						75.745 7.506	0.732 (14.246)	0.757 (0.875)	13.824 (85.015 (1, 26))	11.877 (28)
29	"	38.004 Tr 1.102	47.271 F 4.916					-36.626 7.328	0.975 (4.373)	0.978 (0.990)	4.175 (5.96 × 10 ² (2, 25))	3.066 (28)
30	"	36.018 F 6.454	-56.836 B 7.816	19.125 N _V 0.506				-24.248 8.138	0.978 (4.060)	0.981 (0.992)	3.818 (4.77 × 10 ² (3, 24))	2.584 (28)
31	"	60.050 F 5.565	18.572 N _V 0.570	-6.975 N _B 1.196				-51.774 7.551	0.972 (4.609)	0.975 (0.989)	4.395 (3.58 × 10 ² (3, 24))	2.989 (28)
32	"	41.960 F 4.823	19.087 N _V 0.420	-8.308 N _P 0.893				-14.100 6.653	0.985 (3.382)	0.987 (0.994)	3.184 (6.89 × 10 ² (3, 24))	1.976 (28)
33	"	39.394 F 6.010	19.158 N _V 0.435	-17.867 N _X 2.490	-8.202 N _V 0.914			-27.955 7.589	0.984 (3.481)	0.987 (0.994)	3.216 (5.07 × 10 ² (4, 23))	1.895 (28)
34	Polyols	17.609 Tr 5.531	68.152 F 6.088						0.859 (11.864)	0.890 (0.951)	11.072 (1.74 × 10 ³ (2, 7))	6.841 (9)
35	"	69.629 F 5.587	7.503 N _V 2.335						0.866 (11.550)	0.892 (0.951)	11.011 (1.76 × 10 ³ (2, 7))	7.243 (9)
36	Alcohol**	34.701 Tr 2.292	67.994 F 2.638						0.942 (10.369)	0.952 (0.977)	9.588 (3.57 × 10 ² (2, 34))	5.757 (37)
37	"	68.545 F 2.819	-27.273 B 12.645	17.243 N _V 1.171				-48.251 9.304	0.940 (10.550)	0.951 (0.977)	9.680 (2.33 × 10 ² (3, 33))	5.890 (37)
38	"	69.066 F 2.597	16.877 N _V 1.057	-6.371 N _B 2.116				-49.833 8.259	0.948 (9.811)	0.956 (0.980)	9.159 (2.62 × 10 ² (3, 33))	5.122 (37)
39	"	68.216 F 2.676	17.436 N _V 1.111	-5.397 N _P 1.858				-40.980 9.085	0.947 (9.921)	0.955 (0.979)	9.227 (2.58 × 10 ² (3, 33))	5.297 (37)
40	"	68.650 F 2.727	17.136 N _V 1.164	-8.574 N _X 4.479	-6.337 N _V 2.140			-50.363 9.308	0.947 (9.941)	0.955 (0.980)	9.256 (1.92 × 10 ² (4, 32))	5.011 (37)
41	Alkanes	57.836 T 1.435						-97.760 5.099	0.968 (5.633)	0.970 (0.985)	5.496 (1.62 × 10 ³ (1, 49))	3.998 (51)
42	"	-38.801 B 3.830	28.597 N _V 0.582					-105.643 4.251	0.977 (4.723)	0.981 (0.991)	4.437 (1.26 × 10 ³ (2, 48))	3.381 (51)
43	"	27.936 N _V 0.910	-5.654 N _B 1.364					-103.086 6.473	0.950 (7.052)	0.955 (0.978)	6.745 (5.32 × 10 ² (2, 48))	5.037 (51)
44	"	29.061 N _V 0.756	-5.893 N _P 0.806					-96.555 5.107	0.967 (5.684)	0.971 (0.986)	5.404 (8.41 × 10 ² (2, 48))	4.239 (51)
45	"	29.022 N _V 0.755	-12.141 N _X 1.639	-5.064 N _V 1.096				-108.648 6.156	0.967 (5.760)	0.971 (0.986)	5.391 (5.64 × 10 ² (3, 47))	4.167 (51)
46	Amines	38.665 T 6.163						43.181 10.287	0.599 (22.380)	0.657 (0.821)	21.191 (39.360 (1, 19))	15.199 (21)
47	"	47.879 Tr 3.111	-15.370 F 4.054					-23.885 9.482	0.902 (11.086)	0.924 (0.965)	9.979 (1.23 × 10 ² (2, 18))	7.821 (21)

Table-3 (contd.)

48	"	-16.683F 3.891	-74.377B 14.986	23.716N _V 1.472	-20.649 11.929	0.904 (10.961)	0.932 (0.971)	9.408 (93.036 (3, 17))	7.063 (21)
49	"	-12.207F 3.929	24.861N _V 1.588	-15.469N _B 3.372	-33.546 12.314	0.904 (10.560)	0.926 (0.968)	9.841 (84.543 (3, 17))	7.606 (21)
50	"	-15.422F 3.288	24.478N _V 1.159	-12.949N _P 1.872		0.925 (9.678)	0.945 (0.975)	8.519 (1.10 × 10 ³ (3, 18))	6.574 (21)
51	"	-15.753F 3.996	24.394N _V 1.475	-26.749N _X 6.306	-24.945 12.295	0.902 (11.069)	0.938 (0.975)	9.025 (76.439 (4, 16))	6.566 (21)
52	Ethers	38.450T 5.614			29.402 10.618	0.799 (14.033)	0.836 (0.924)	13.358 (46.909 (1, 8))	10.081 (10)
53	"	48.692T _R 2.536			-75.157 9.067	0.965 (5.886)	0.976 (0.989)	5.101 (3.69 × 10 ² (1, 8))	3.610 (10)
54	"	-52.319B 12.262	24.196N _V 1.435		-77.688 11.270	0.939 (7.737)	0.973 (0.989)	5.418 (1.63 × 10 ² (2, 7))	3.561 (10)
55	"	26.305N _V 1.038	-12.682N _B 1.953		-92.290 7.739	0.981 (4.316)	0.986 (0.995)	3.879 (3.22 × 10 ² (2, 7))	2.694 (10)
56	"	24.993N _V 0.988	-8.950N _P 1.330		-64.478 8.496	0.970 (5.462)	0.987 (0.995)	3.761 (3.42 × 10 ² (2, 7))	2.544 (10)
57	"	25.659N _V 0.943	-16.290N _X 2.498	-11.365N _V 1.792	-86.892 7.245	0.979 (4.583)	0.990 (0.997)	3.291 (2.99 × 10 ² (3, 6))	2.005 (10)
58	Halocarbons	52.862T _R 5.539	30.747F 3.971		-98.178 12.800	0.926 (10.258)	0.939 (0.973)	9.579 (1.24 × 10 ² (2, 14))	6.385 (17)
59	"	35.666F 3.471	28.071N _V 2.659		-129.307 13.927	0.938 (9.350)	0.949 (0.977)	8.767 (1.50 × 10 ² (2, 15))	6.157 (17)
60	"	31.523F 3.346	14.822N _I 3.902			0.754 (18.662)	0.780 (0.891)	18.192 (2.70 × 10 ² (2, 15))	13.737 (17)
61	Mixed	39.441T _R 4.180	22.934F 3.116		-33.336 15.178	0.411 (34.083)	0.438 (0.668)	33.396 (53.675 (2, 133))	22.864 (136)
62	"	24.079F 3.445	-24.160B 19.954	19.708N _V 2.093	-41.024 15.061	0.408 (34.157)	0.437 (0.670)	33.444 (35.885 (3, 132))	22.611 (136)
63	"	12.135F 1.950	-40.706B 10.675	19.678N _V 1.116	-41.244 8.558	0.829 (18.377)	0.840 (0.919)	17.827 (1.78 × 10 ² (4, 131))	14.165 (136)
64	"	6.071F 2.072	-50.953B 9.812	21.944N _V 1.087	-55.092 8.413	0.859 (16.698)	0.870 (0.935)	16.093 (1.81 × 10 ² (5, 130))	12.953 (136)
65	"	7.824F 2.158	21.519N _V 1.158	-7.064N _B 2.201	-56.153 9.014	0.842 (17.648)	0.854 (0.927)	17.022 (1.59 × 10 ² (5, 130))	13.440 (136)
66	"	6.179F 2.150	22.262N _V 1.144	-7.500N _P 1.661	-42.125 10.296	0.852 (17.059)	0.864 (0.932)	16.442 (1.72 × 10 ² (5, 130))	13.176 (136)
67	"	6.139F 2.152	22.288N _V 1.145	-16.166N _X 3.560	-57.815 8.815	0.851 (17.134)	0.864 (0.933)	16.452 (1.43 × 10 ² (6, 129))	13.203 (136)

s.e. = standard error; F values are significant at 99% level [df = np, n-np-i, np = no. of predictor variables; i = 1 if intercept is present; i = 0, otherwise].

*t values of the regression coefficients and constants are significant at 95% level [df = n-np-i].

**Monohydric alkanols and polyols.

about 95%. From the equations, it is evident that bulk and functionality have positive contributions while branching has negative contribution to boiling point.

Table 3 shows the relations of boiling point of alkanes, amines, ethers and halocarbons with topochemical indices. In all cases, explained variance and predicted variance of the best equations of individual series are more than 90%. For alkanes, amines and ethers, the relations show positive contributions of bulk and functionality and negative contribution of branching. In case of halocarbons, positive contributions of functionality and branching are observed. The calculated values according to eqs. 42, 51, 56 and 59 are shown in Table 1. 2,2-Dimethylpropane (**53**), 2,2,3,3-tetramethylbutane (**85**) and 2,2,3,3-tetramethylpentane (**99**) act as outliers for eq. 42 while the other eqs. (51, 56 and 59) have no outliers.

Table 3 shows the relations of boiling point of the composite set (alcohols, alkanes, amines, ethers and halocarbons) with different topochemical parameters. For the composite set, one integer variable I_{NOH} denoting number of hydroxy groups and one indicator variable I_{Hal} denoting presence or absence of halogen atoms in the compounds, had to be defined. The results suggest that apart from positive contributions of bulk and functionality and negative contribution of branching, boiling point specifically increases with increase in number of hydroxy groups and presence of halogen atoms. The final equation (64) could explain 87.0% of the variance (predicted variance 85.9%). The calculated values according to this equation are given in Table 1. Only two compounds, ethanediol (**38**) and 1,3-propanediol (**40**) act as outliers for the equation.

Conclusion :

This study shows that though first order composite topochemical index T does not always provide acceptable model for molar thermochemical properties of heterofunctional compounds, TAU scheme can generate statistically acceptable relations when the first order composite index is partitioned into different components like skeletal index, size and shape factors, branching and functionality. Further, TAU indices can decode specific contributions of molecular bulk (size), functionality, branching and shape parameters to the thermochemical properties. In general, the properties increase with increase in molecular bulk and functionality, and decrease with increase in branching. Further, boiling point specifically increase with increase in number of hydroxy groups in alcohols and presence of halogen atoms in halocarbons. The study suggests that TAU scheme has significant potential and diagnostic feature in exploring QSPR of diverse functional compounds.

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